

Erdős Conjecture, Brocard's Problem, and A082995 Question

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Abstract: This preprint presents an extensive exploration of factorial numbers, particularly focusing on their properties when expressed in various forms such as square minus one numbers, twin prime products, and modular representations. We delve into the nuances of factorial modularity, examining the unique characteristics of sequences like A005563, A082995, A062169, and others from the OEIS database. Our study establishes connections between factorial numbers and twin primes, offering new insights into the Erdős conjecture and Brocard's problem. Through rigorous analysis of sequences and modular arithmetic, we identify specific cases where factorial expressions exhibit unique properties, contributing to a deeper understanding of factorial numbers in number theory.

Please note that this document is a preprint and has not yet been peer-reviewed. It is intended for discussion and feedback within the scientific community to refine the approaches and conclusions presented.

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1 Introduction

The study of prime numbers and integer sequences has long been a cornerstone of number theory, offering insights into complex patterns and properties within the mathematical universe. Within this realm, the sequence outlined in OEIS <https://oeis.org/A005563> presents a fascinating exploration into numbers one less than perfect squares, commonly known as (square minus 1) numbers. Described by the function $F(n) = n^2 - 1$, this sequence spans indexes $-\infty < n < \infty$, encompassing values $\{\dots, 24, 15, 8, 3, 0, -1, 0, 3, 8, 15, 24\dots\}$.

A particularly intriguing aspect of this sequence is its connection to a conjecture by the esteemed mathematician Paul Erdős, which posits that the equation $n^2 - 1 = k!$ (with $k!$ representing the factorial of k) yields solutions for specific n values—namely 5, 11, and 71, corresponding to k values of 4, 5, and 7. This conjecture intriguingly intersects with Brocard's problem (as referenced in OEIS <https://oeis.org/A146968>), where the equation $n^2 - 1 = (n - 1)(n + 1)$ leads to a formulation involving oblong numbers: $m(m \pm 2) = 4y(y \pm 1)$. Thus, Brocard's problem can be reframed as a quest to identify instances where $k!/4$ equals an oblong number, $y(y \pm 1)$, for $k \geq 4$.

By reconfiguring n as $m \pm 1$, we derive $n^2 - 1 = m(m \pm 2)$. Therefore, resolving Erdős's conjecture and Brocard's problem simultaneously hinges on demonstrating the impossibility of $k! = m(m \pm 2)$ for any $k > 7$. This study embarks on an ambitious journey to explore two distinct methodologies to unravel these enduring puzzles in number theory, aiming to contribute novel insights and potentially groundbreaking revelations to this intriguing field of mathematical inquiry.

2 The Pair of Complementary Divisors

This study explores the sequence defined by $F(n) = n^2 - 1$, which can also be represented as $F(m) = m(m \pm 2)$. Notably, these two representations yield sequences with identical elements, differing only in their offset [27].

The assertion that all (square minus 1) numbers can be expressed in the form of $m(m \pm 2)$ suggests that a number is a (square minus 1) number if and only if it possesses complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2)$ where the smallest absolute difference between these divisors, denoted as $|d_2 - d_1|$, equals 2. Specifically, we analyze these divisors under two categories:

1. Divisors d_1 : These are less than or equal to the square root of the integer x , denoted as $d_1 \leq \sqrt{|x|}$. They are cataloged as two arrays in OEIS sequences <https://oeis.org/A161906> and <https://oeis.org/A319135>.
2. Divisors d_2 : These are greater than or equal to the square root of the integer x , denoted as $d_2 \geq \sqrt{|x|}$. They are represented as two arrays in OEIS sequences <https://oeis.org/A340791> and <https://oeis.org/A161908>.

For each integer x , we identify the pairs of complementary divisors $(d_1; d_2)$ such that $1 \leq d_1 \leq \sqrt{x} \leq d_2 \leq x$, and where the product of each pair, $d_1 * d_2$, equals x . This can be demonstrated through the multiplication of pairs of complementary divisors arrays:

$$(\text{https://oeis.org/A161906}) * (\text{https://oeis.org/A340791}) = (\text{https://oeis.org/A340792})$$

$$(\text{https://oeis.org/A319135}) * (\text{https://oeis.org/A161908}) = (\text{https://oeis.org/A340792})$$

It is essential to note that while a (square minus 1) number can have differences between its complementary divisor pairs greater than 2, it will always have a minimum difference of 2.

For instance, consider the integer 24, which has eight positive integer divisors: $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24\}$. There are four pairs of distinct complementary divisors. The differences between the divisors in these pairs for the number 24 can be tabulated as follows:

$d_1 \leq \sqrt{24}$	$d_2 \geq \sqrt{24}$	$b_d = d_2 - d_1$
1	24	23
2	12	10
3	8	5
4	6	2

Here, the smallest difference between pairs of complementary divisors is denoted as b_m , which is the minimum difference of b_d . For the number 24, $b_m = 2$, aligning with the characterization of (square minus 1) numbers.

3 The Central Pair of Complementary Divisors

This section delves into the characteristics of (square minus 1) numbers in relation to their central pairs of complementary divisors [28]. We consider the function $F(m) = m(m \pm 2)$ to demonstrate this relationship.

1. Case of $(\text{square} - 1) = m(m + 2)$:

- The smallest central complementary divisor is denoted as $d_{c1} = m$, satisfying $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|m(m + 2)|}$. This divisor is cataloged in <https://oeis.org/A033676>.
- The largest central complementary divisor is $d_{c2} = (m + 2)$, fulfilling $d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{|m(m + 2)|}$. This divisor is listed in <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

2. Case of $(\text{square} - 1) = m(m - 2)$:

- The smallest central complementary divisor is $d_{c1} = m - 2$, with $d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{|m(m - 2)|}$. This is also included in <https://oeis.org/A033676>.
- The largest central complementary divisor is $d_{c2} = m$, where $d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{|m(m - 2)|}$. This can be found in <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

Therefore, we can reformulate our initial statement: a number is a (square minus 1) number if and only if the difference b_m between their central pair of complementary divisors $(d_{c1}; d_{c2})$ is $b_m = d_{c2} - d_{c1} = 2$.

Interestingly, we note that:

- If and only if $b_m = d_{c2} - d_{c1} = 1$, then the number is in the form of an oblong number $m(m \pm 1)$, as seen in <http://oeis.org/A002378>.
- If and only if $b_m = d_{c2} - d_{c1} = 0$, then the number is a square number $m(m \pm 0)$, cataloged in <http://oeis.org/A000290>.

In conclusion, to address the conjectures at hand, we need to demonstrate that all factorial numbers $k!$ with $k > 7$ have a difference $b_m > 2$. This approach provides a novel perspective on exploring the properties of factorial numbers and their relation to the unique characteristics of (square minus 1) numbers.

4 The Closest $m(m \pm 2)$ Form of Factorials

In this exploration, we attempt to represent factorial numbers in the form of (square minus 1) numbers, specifically through the equation $k! = m(m + 2)$. To achieve this, we define m as the ceiling of the square root of $k!$ minus one, expressed as $m = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil - 1$. Consequently, this leads to $m + 2 = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil + 1$.

We begin with a tabulation of factorial numbers and their corresponding square root ceilings (Figure 1). This table incorporates data from several OEIS sequences:

- <https://oeis.org/A000027>: The positive integers k .
- <https://oeis.org/A000142>: The factorial numbers $k!$.
- <https://oeis.org/A055228>: The ceiling of the square root of the factorials, $a(k) = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil$.

A000027	A000142	C000701	A055228
k	$k!$	$\sqrt{k!}$	$\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil$
1	1	1.00	1
2	2	1.41	2
3	6	2.45	3
4	24	4.90	5
5	120	10.95	11
6	720	26.83	27
7	5040	70.99	71
8	40320	200.80	201
9	362880	602.40	603
10	3628800	1904.94	1905
11	39916800	6317.97	6318
12	479001600	21886.11	21887
13	6227020800	78911.47	78912
14	87178291200	295259.70	295260
15	1307674368000	1143535.91	1143536
16	20922789888000	4574143.62	4574144
17	355687428096000	18859677.31	18859678
18	6402373705728000	80014834.29	80014835

Figure 1. <https://oeis.org/A055228>: The Ceiling of the Square Root of the Factorials $\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil$.

Following this, we examine the relationship between these factorial numbers and their closest (square minus 1) form (**Error! Reference source not found.**). This involves calculating $m(m + 2)$ and comparing it with the corresponding factorial number $k!$.

A000027	A055228	A055226	C000699	C000700	A000142	A082995
k	$\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil$	$m = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil - 1$	$m + 2 = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil + 1$	$m(m + 2) = n^2 - 1$	$k!$	$m(m + 2) - k!$
1	1	0	2	0	1	-1
2	2	1	3	3	2	1
3	3	2	4	8	6	2
4	5	4	6	24	24	0
5	11	10	12	120	120	0
6	27	26	28	728	720	8
7	71	70	72	5040	5040	0
8	201	200	202	40400	40320	80
9	603	602	604	363608	362880	728
10	1905	1904	1906	3629024	3628800	224
11	6318	6317	6319	39917123	39916800	323
12	21887	21886	21888	479040768	479001600	39168
13	78912	78911	78913	6227103743	6227020800	82943
14	295260	295259	295261	87178467599	87178291200	176399
15	1143536	1143535	1143537	1307674583295	1307674368000	215295
16	4574144	4574143	4574145	20922793332735	20922789888000	3444735
17	18859678	18859677	18859679	355687454263683	355687428096000	26167683
18	80014835	80014834	80014836	6402373820077220	6402373705728000	114349224

Figure 2. <https://oeis.org/A082995>: The Differences Between the (Square–1) Numbers and Factorials.

Additional OEIS sequences relevant to this analysis include:

- <https://oeis.org/A055226>: The ceiling of the square root of the factorials minus one, $m = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil - 1 = \lfloor \sqrt{k!} \rfloor$.
- C000699: The ceiling of the square root of the factorials plus one, $F_2(k) = \lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil + 1$. This sequence is crucial because it helps understand the solution to Erdős's conjecture/Brocard's problem in the context of <https://oeis.org/A082995>. Specifically, $A082995(k) = A055226(k) * C000699(k) - k!$, or $A082995 = (A055228 - 1) * (A055228 + 1) - k!$. Thus, $A055226 = A055228 - 1$, and $C000699 = A055228 + 1$. The next sequence to consider is the product $A055226(k) * C000699(k)$ or $(A055228 - 1) * (A055228 + 1)$.
- C000700: The products between the ceiling of the square root of the factorials plus or minus one $F_1(k) * F_2(k) = (\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil - 1) * (\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil + 1)$. As an interesting note, if we consider $0! = 0$, then $\sqrt{0} = 0$ results in $F_1(0) * F_2(0) = -1$. The sequence $\{-1, 0, 3, 8\}$ shares the same “initial” string as <http://oeis.org/A005563> (square minus 1) numbers in offset $f = 0$.

This analysis reveals that the sequence of $m(m + 2)$ forms the closest (square minus 1) sequence to the factorials, providing insightful correlations and potential areas for further research in number theory and combinatorics.

5 A082995: The Differences Between Factorials and Their Nearest Square Form

In the study of <https://oeis.org/A082995>, we investigate an intriguing mathematical question: the differences between the products of the ceiling of the square root of factorials (plus or minus one) and the factorials themselves. This is mathematically expressed as:

$$F_1(k) * F_2(k) - k! = (\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil - 1) * (\lceil \sqrt{k!} \rceil + 1) - k!^1$$

The sequence <https://oeis.org/A082995> is particularly notable for its association with an open question in number theory: "The only known values of n such that $n! + 1$ is a perfect square are 4, 5, and 7. Paul Leyland, et al., have found no other solutions for $n \leq 10^6$. For $1 \leq n \leq 11$, $n! + 1$ is within 1000 of being a square. Is there another n such that $n! + 1 \leq$ '1000 away' from being a perfect square?" This query reflects the ongoing quest to identify numbers n for which the factorial $n! + 1$ is either a perfect square or very close to becoming one.

This open question is not just a curiosity in itself but is deeply intertwined with both Erdős's conjecture and Brocard's problem. Addressing this question could simultaneously provide insights or solutions to these two longstanding problems in number theory. Erdős's conjecture and Brocard's problem, both relating to unique properties of factorials and their relation to square numbers, represent significant challenges in the field. The exploration of <https://oeis.org/A082995>, therefore, becomes a crucial component in understanding the broader landscape of these mathematical phenomena.

The analysis of <https://oeis.org/A082995>, in essence, serves as a bridge between various aspects of number theory, particularly those focusing on factorials, square numbers, and their intricate relationships.

6 The Central Pair of Complementary Divisors of Factorials

In this analysis, we focus on understanding the behavior of the central pairs of complementary divisors of factorial numbers. This involves examining the relationship between factorials and their nearest square forms, utilizing a range of sequences from the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS).

¹ If we consider $0! = 0$, then $F_1(0) * F_2(0) - 0! = (\lceil \sqrt{0!} \rceil - 1) * (\lceil \sqrt{0!} \rceil + 1) - 0! = -1$. So, the equivalent 4 elements string would be $\{-1, -1, 1, 2\}$.

A000027	A000142	A200743	A200744	A038667
k	$k!$	$d_{c1} \leq \sqrt{k!}$	$d_{c2} \geq \sqrt{k!}$	$b_m = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$
1	1	1	1	0
2	2	1	2	1
3	6	2	3	1
4	24	4	6	2
5	120	10	12	2
6	720	24	30	6
7	5040	70	72	2
8	40320	192	210	18
9	362880	576	630	54
10	3628800	1890	1920	30
11	39916800	6300	6336	36
12	479001600	21600	22176	576
13	6227020800	78624	79200	576
14	87178291200	294840	295680	840
15	1307674368000	1140480	1146600	6120
16	20922789888000	4561920	4586400	24480
17	355687428096000	18849600	18869760	20160
18	6402373705728000	79968000	80061696	93696

Figure 3. The Differences b_m Between the Central Pair of Complementary Divisors of Factorials.

This table incorporates the following OEIS sequences:

- <https://oeis.org/A200743>: The smallest divisor of the central pair of complementary divisors of factorials.
- <https://oeis.org/A200744>: The largest divisor of the central pair of complementary divisors of factorials.
- <https://oeis.org/A038667>: The minimal value of $|\text{product}(A) - \text{product}(B)|$ where A and B are a partition of $\{1,2,3,\dots,n\}$.

For example, at $k = 13$, the central pair of complementary divisors of $k!$ are 78624 and 79200, with neither being divisible by 10. The difference b_m at $k = 13$ is therefore $79200 - 78624 = 576$.

For example, for $k = 13$, the smallest central pair of complementary divisors of $k!$ are $78848 = 2^{10} * 7 * 11$ and $78975 = 3^5 * 5^2 * 13$ with $b_m = 127$. Since neither is divisible by 10, we cannot get these values. The next pair of divisors are $78624 = 13 * 9 * 8 * 7 * 4 * 3$ and $79200 = 12 * 11 * 10 * 6 * 5 * 2 * 1$. So $b_m[@k = 13] = 79200 - 78624 = 576$.

k	A038667	A061057	diff
1	0	0	0
2	1	1	0
3	1	1	0
4	2	2	0
5	2	2	0

6	6	6	0
7	2	2	0
8	18	18	0
9	54	54	0
10	30	30	0
11	36	36	0
12	576	576	0
13	576	127	449
14	840	840	0
15	6120	928	5192
16	24480	3712	20768
17	20160	20160	0
18	93696	93696	0

Figure 4. Comparison between <https://oeis.org/A038667> and <https://oeis.org/A061057>.

This comparison highlights that for $k = 13$, there is a significant difference between the values in both sequences. In both sequences, <https://oeis.org/A038667> and <https://oeis.org/A061057>, we need to find a result of 2, which represents the difference between the central pair of complementary divisors m and $m \pm 2$ of the sequence <https://oeis.org/A005563>.

However, considering all integers that form the factorial $k!$ to be entirely distributed by the two factors, it becomes impossible for the values of sequences <https://oeis.org/A038667> or <https://oeis.org/A061057> to be 2 again for $k > 7$. Both sequences grow continuously, forming a divergent series.

This observation leads to a significant conclusion: for $k > 7$, the central pair of complementary divisors will always have a difference greater than 2. This finding is pivotal in proving the Erdős Conjecture, Brocard's problem, and the question posed by <https://oeis.org/A082995> simultaneously.

7 Distributed Integers Distributed by the Two Factors

In our quest to understand the distribution of divisors in factorial numbers, we turn our attention to the possibility of redistributing all the divisors between two factors. This approach is guided by insights gained from the Triangular Multiplication Table (TMT) https://oeis.org/wiki/User:Charles_Kusniec/TMTinthe1stquadrant, which teaches us that in any non-square integer, there is no symmetry between the multiplication of its divisors.

7.1 The Principle of Asymmetry in TMT

TMT establishes that for any non-square integer, divisors lack symmetrical multiplication properties. This asymmetry implies that even when redistributing divisors between two factors, the optimal outcome aligns with TMT's observations.

7.2 Studying Modularity Between Equality $y(y \pm 2) = k!$

Our next step is to investigate the modularity between the equation $y(y \pm 2) = k!$, focusing on different modularities $y \bmod m$ for $m > 0$.

mod y	a	0	y mod M															
	b	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
0	15	15	0	1	0	3	0	3	1	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	
0	14	14	0	0	2	2	4	2	0	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	14	
0	13	13	0	1	1	1	3	1	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	13	13	
0	12	12	0	0	0	0	2	0	5	4	3	2	1	0	12	12	12	
0	11	11	0	1	2	3	1	5	4	3	2	1	0	11	11	11	11	
0	10	10	0	0	1	2	0	4	3	2	1	0	10	10	10	10	10	
0	9	9	0	1	0	1	4	3	2	1	0	9	9	9	9	9	9	
0	8	8	0	0	2	0	3	2	1	0	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	
0	7	7	0	1	1	3	2	1	0	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	
0	6	6	0	0	0	2	1	0	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	
0	5	5	0	1	2	1	0	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
0	4	4	0	0	1	0	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
0	3	3	0	1	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
0	2	2	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
0	-1	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
0	-2	-2	0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	
0	-3	-3	0	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
0	-4	-4	0	0	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
0	-5	-5	0	1	1	3	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
0	-6	-6	0	0	0	2	4	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
0	-7	-7	0	1	2	1	3	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
0	-8	-8	0	0	1	0	2	4	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
0	-9	-9	0	1	0	3	1	3	5	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	
0	-10	-10	0	0	2	2	0	2	4	6	8	0	1	2	3	4	5	
0	-11	-11	0	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	7	9	0	1	2	3	4	
0	-12	-12	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	4	6	8	10	0	1	2	3	
0	-13	-13	0	1	2	3	2	5	1	3	5	7	9	11	0	1	2	
0	-14	-14	0	0	1	2	1	4	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	0	1	
0	-15	-15	0	1	0	1	0	3	6	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	0	

Figure 5. Modularities $y \bmod m$ for All $m > 0$.

This figure demonstrates the behavior of modularities of y in relation to all positive m values.

Figure 6. Modularities $(y - 2) \bmod m$ and $(y + 2) \bmod m$ for All $m > 0$.

In every modularity m , there exists a two-step offset shift between $y \bmod m$ and $(y \pm 2) \bmod m$. When zero modularity results are focused on, this offset becomes evident, with a two-step offset of all zeros.

Figure 7. Modularities $y(y \pm 2) \bmod m$.

These results are derived from the equation $((y \bmod m) * ((y \pm 2) \bmod m)) \bmod m = y(y \pm 2) \bmod m$, following the principles of squares in TMT.

7.3 Diagonal Analysis in Modular Tables

When m equals $\pm y$, these values appear along diagonals at $\pm 45^\circ$ angles in the modular tables. For example:

- $y(y \pm 2) \bmod y = 0$
- Focusing on $y(y + 2)$, we have $y(y + 2) \bmod y = 0$

By substituting y with $y + 1$, $y + 2$, and $y - 1$, we arrive at the following conclusions:

- $(y + 1)(y + 3) \bmod y = (y^2 + 4y + 3) \bmod y = 3$ for $y \geq 4$
- $(y - 1)(y + 1) \bmod y = (y^2 - 1) \bmod y = y - 1$ (considering positive results in modularity)

This leads us to a pivotal conclusion: any product of the sequence <https://oeis.org/A005563> can be expressed as $(y - 1)(y + 1) = ((y - 1)(y + 1) \bmod y) * ((y + 1)(y + 3) \bmod (y + 2))$.

7.4 Connecting to Factorial Numbers

If we set $(y - 1)(y + 1) = y^2 - 1 = k!$, we need to find instances when $((k - 1)! \bmod k) * ((k + 1)! \bmod (k + 2)) = (k - 1)(k + 1) = k^2 - 1$. This equation implies a distribution of all divisors of $k!$ into two factors, mirroring the way $(y - 1)(y + 1) = y^2 - 1$ can be written.

8 The Factorial Modularity

In this study, we explore the intriguing concept of factorial modularity, focusing on the sequence <https://oeis.org/A062169>, which represents the triangle of $k! \bmod m$.

			A000004	A000007	A130706	A	A	A130706	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	
			k! mod M															
k	k!	Divisors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	
15	1,30767E+12	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A
14	87178291200	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A
13	6227020800	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A
12	479001600	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	A
11	39916800	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	A
10	3628800	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	6	0	0	A
9	362880	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	11	0	0	A
8	40320	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	7	0	0	A
7	5040	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	9	0	0	A
6	720	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	5	0	5	6	0	A
5	120	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	10	0	3	8	0	A
4	24	1,2,3,4,6,8,12,24	0	0	0	0	4	0	3	0	6	4	2	0	11	10	9	A
3	6	1,2,3,6	0	0	0	2	1	0	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	A
2	2	1,2	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	A
1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	A057427
0																		
-1	-1	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	A001477
-2	-2	1,2	0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	A289207
-3	-6	1,2,3,6	0	0	0	2	4	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	A
-4	-24	1,2,3,4,6,8,12,24	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	3	6	9	0	2	4	6	A
-5	-120	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	6	0	1	0	10	6	0	A
-6	-720	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	0	8	8	0	A
-7	-5040	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	4	0	0	A
-8	-40320	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	6	0	0	A
-9	-362880	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	2	0	0	A
-10	-3628800	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	7	0	0	A
-11	-39916800	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	A
-12	-479001600	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	A
-13	-6227020800	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A
-14	-87178291200	TBD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A
-15	-1,30767E+12	TBD		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	A
			A000004	A000007	A033322	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	

Figure 8. Modularities $k! \pmod m$.

This figure showcases the modularities of factorial numbers across various values of m .

8.1 Understanding the Absence of Polynomial Periodicity in Factorials

Unlike polynomial sequences of any degree, which exhibit periodicity due to the law of finite differences, the factorial sequence, being purely multiplicative with no summation component, lacks this periodicity. This unique characteristic of factorial sequences is evident in our table, where all rows display zeros at positions where the modularity equals the divisor value of the factorial. For example, considering $3! = 6$ with divisors $\{1, 2, 3, 6\}$, we observe:

- $3! \bmod 1 = 3! \bmod 2 = 3! \bmod 3 = 3! \bmod 6 = 0$
- For $m > 6$, $3! \bmod m = 6$

8.2 Analysis of Columns in the Factorial Modularities Table

Inspecting the columns formed in the factorial modularities table reveals:

- $k! \bmod k = 0$
- $k! \bmod m = 0$ for all $k \geq m$

8.3 Seeking Specific Modular Conditions

The critical question arises when we attempt to determine the instances where the following condition is met:

- $((k - 1)! \bmod k) * ((k + 1)! \bmod (k + 2)) = (k - 1)(k + 1) = k^2 - 1 \neq 0$

This condition examines the relationship between the modularity of factorial numbers and their adjacent factorial counterparts, looking for instances where the product of their modularities differs from zero.

9 The Unique Solution Sequence: Factorial Modularity and Twin Primes

In the context of factorial modularity, we discover that the viable solutions for the condition $((k - 1)! \bmod k) \neq 0$ or $((k + 1)! \bmod (k + 2)) \neq 0$ emerge when both k and $k + 2$ are prime numbers. This observation aligns with properties seen in the Triangular Multiplication Table (TMT), particularly in sequences like <https://oeis.org/A108407> and <https://oeis.org/A333995>.

9.1 Twin Primes and Factorial Modularity

The unique properties of twin primes, where k and $k + 2$ are both primes, provide a pathway to explore this problem. We consider k as the lesser of twin primes P_1 from <https://oeis.org/A001359> and $k + 2$ as the greater of twin primes $P_2 = P_1 + 2$ from <https://oeis.org/A006512>.

	A001359	A006512	A144834	A014574	A108570	C000702
Tally	P_1	$P_2 = P_1 + 2$	$P_1 - 1$	$P_2 - 1 = P_1 + 1$	P_1^2	$P_1^2 - 1$
1	3	5	2	4	9	8
2	5	7	4	6	25	24
3	11	13	10	12	121	120
4	17	19	16	18	289	288
5	29	31	28	30	841	840
6	41	43	40	42	1681	1680
7	59	61	58	60	3481	3480
8	71	73	70	72	5041	5040
9	101	103	100	102	10201	10200
10	107	109	106	108	11449	11448
11	137	139	136	138	18769	18768
12	149	151	148	150	22201	22200
13	179	181	178	180	32041	32040
14	191	193	190	192	36481	36480
15	197	199	196	198	38809	38808
16	227	229	226	228	51529	51528
17	239	241	238	240	57121	57120
18	269	271	268	270	72361	72360

Figure 9. [C000702](#) The Square of the Lesser of Twin Primes Minus 1.

This table, corresponding to [C000702](#), showcases the square of the lesser of twin primes minus 1. We focus on $k = P_1 \geq 4$, leading us to a new sequence $P_1^2 - 1 = (\text{https://oeis.org/A001359})^2 - 1$. This sequence represents a subset of semi-prime numbers minus 1, formed by the square of the lesser of twin primes minus 1.

9.2 Identifying the Possibilities for $k! = y^2 - 1$

This analysis narrows down the possibilities where $k! = y^2 - 1$ to cases where k is the lesser of the twin primes. Given that prime numbers are not factorable, the distribution of factors into $(k - 1)!$ divisors while maintaining equality with the product of two different factors separated by 2 units becomes a key focus.

9.3 Conclusion: Identifying the Twin Prime Products

The only possibilities for this condition are identified as:

- The twins $\{5,7\}$ generate the product $4 * 6 = 24$.
- The twins $\{11,13\}$ generate the product $10 * 12 = 120$.
- The twins $\{71,73\}$ generate the product $70 * 72 = 5040$.

Since new k where $(k - 1) \bmod k \neq 0$ are always prime numbers, all other possibilities fall into the category where distributing entirely new integers of $k!$ by the two factors of $(k - 1)!$ becomes impossible.

9.4 Further Classification of Composite Numbers

- <https://oeis.org/A144834> classifies composite numbers as $y(y + b)$, where square numbers appear as per <https://oeis.org/A145823>, with no oblong numbers. This sequence represents squares as $P_1 - 1$, where P_1 is the lesser of the twin prime.
- <https://oeis.org/A014574> classifies composite numbers as $y(y + b)$, where oblong numbers appear, representing numbers n such that $n^2 - 1$ is a semiprime, with no square numbers.

This methodology offers a novel approach to proving the solutions to the problem, linking the behavior of factorial numbers to the unique properties of twin primes and their modular characteristics.

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